

DEVELOPMENT OF A DASHBOARD FOR ELECTRICAL NETWORKS: ENVISIONING THE ELECTRICAL INFRASTRUCTURE (AS AN EXAMPLE OF SAMARKAND REGION)

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Abstrakt. Ushbu maqolada biz ArcGIS Online yordamida boshqaruv panelini ishlab chiqish va joriy etish orqali Samarqand viloyatida elektr energiyasi infratuzilmasini boshqarishga kompleks yondashuvni taqdim etamiz. Elektr infratuzilmasini boshqarish energiya taqsimlash tizimlarining ishonchligi va samaradorligini ta'minlashda hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi. Boshqaruv paneli manfaatdor tomonlar uchun elektr tarmog'ining turli jihatlarini vizuallashtirish, tahlil qilish va kuzatish uchun markazlashtirilgan platforma bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Boshqaruv panelining asosiy xususiyatlari tuman va tumanlar bo'yicha filtrlarni, shuningdek, nomi va kuchlanish darajasi bo'yicha muayyan elektr liniyalarini tanlash imkoniyatlarini o'z ichiga oladi. Bu foydalanuvchilarga o'z tahlillarini mintaqadagi muayyan qiziqish sohaslariga yo'naltirish imkonini beradi, taqdim etilgan ma'lumotlarning aniqligi va dolzarbligini oshiradi. Ushbu boshqaruv panelining joriy etilishi Samarqand viloyatida elektr energiyasi infratuzilmasini boshqarish amaliyotini modernizatsiya qilish yo'lidagi muhim qadamdir. GIS texnologiyasi va ArcGIS Online quvvatidan foydalangan holda manfaatdor tomonlar elektr infratuzilmasi ma'lumotlariga kirish, tahlil qilish va talqin qilish uchun qulay va intuitiv vositaga ega bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: GAT texnologiyasi, ArcGIS Online, asboblar paneli, elektr infratuzilmasini boshqarish, Samarqand viloyati, manfaatdor tomonlarni jalb qilish, qaror qabul qilish, optimallashtirish, vizualizatsiya, energiya taqsimlash tizimlari.

Аннотация. Управление электроэнергетической инфраструктурой играет ключевую роль в обеспечении надежности и эффективности систем распределения электроэнергии. В данной статье мы представляем комплексный подход к управлению электроэнергетической инфраструктурой в Самаркандской области посредством разработки и внедрения информационной панели с использованием ArcGIS Online. Панель мониторинга служит централизованной платформой для заинтересованных сторон для визуализации, анализа и мониторинга различных аспектов электросети. Ключевые особенности панели управления включают фильтры по районам и подрайонам, а также возможность выбора конкретных линий электропередачи по названию и уровню напряжения. Это позволяет пользователям сосредоточить свой анализ на конкретных областях, представляющих интерес в регионе, повышая степень детализации и актуальность представляемой информации. Внедрение этой информационной панели представляет собой значительный шаг на пути модернизации практики управления электроэнергетической инфраструктурой в Самаркандской области. Используя возможности, ГИС-технологий и ArcGIS Online, заинтересованные стороны получают удобный и интуитивно понятный инструмент для доступа, анализа и интерпретации данных электроэнергетической инфраструктуры.

Ключевые слова: ArcGIS Online, информационная панель, управление электроэнергетической инфраструктурой, Самаркандская область, взаимодействие с заинтересованными сторонами, принятие решений, оптимизация, визуализация, ГИС-технологии, системы распределения электроэнергии.

Abstract. Electricity infrastructure management plays a pivotal role in ensuring the reliability and efficiency of power distribution systems. In this paper, we present a comprehensive approach to electricity infrastructure management in the Samarkand region through the development and implementation of a dashboard using ArcGIS Online. The dashboard serves as a centralized platform for stakeholders to visualize, analyze, and monitor various aspects of the electricity network. Key features of the dashboard include filters by district and sub-district, as well as options to select specific electricity lines by name and voltage level. This enables users to focus their analysis on specific areas of interest within the region, enhancing the granularity and relevance of the information presented. The implementation of this dashboard represents a significant step towards modernizing electricity infrastructure management practices in the Samarkand region. By leveraging the power of GIS technology and ArcGIS Online, stakeholders are empowered with a user-friendly and intuitive tool for accessing, analyzing, and interpreting electricity infrastructure data.

Key words: ArcGIS Online, dashboard, electricity infrastructure management, Samarkand region, stakeholder engagement, decision-making, optimization, visualization, GIS technology, power distribution systems.

Introduction. The management of electricity infrastructure is essential for ensuring the reliability, efficiency, and sustainability of power distribution systems. In regions such as Samarkand, where electricity plays a critical role in supporting economic activities, providing essential services, and enhancing quality of life, effective infrastructure management is paramount [1]. With increasing demands on the electricity grid and growing concerns about environmental impacts and energy security, there is a pressing need for innovative solutions to optimize infrastructure performance and enhance decision-making processes. In response to these challenges, this

paper introduces a novel approach to electricity infrastructure management in the Samarkand region through the development and implementation of a dashboard using ArcGIS Online. ArcGIS Online is a web-based Geographic Information System (GIS) platform that enables users to create, analyze, and share spatial data and maps [2,12]. Leveraging the capabilities of ArcGIS Online, we have developed a user-friendly and interactive dashboard that provides stakeholders with valuable insights into the distribution, characteristics, and performance of the electricity network [3,11].

Figure 1. Flowchart of the methodology.

The dashboard offers a range of features designed to enhance data visualization, analysis, and decision-making. These include filters by district and sub-district, as well as options to select specific electricity lines by name and voltage level. By enabling users to focus their analysis on specific areas of interest within the region, the dashboard facilitates a deeper understanding of the electricity infrastructure and its associated challenges and opportunities. A key highlight of the dashboard is its dynamic visualization capabilities. Upon selection of a particular electricity line, a dynamic bar chart is generated, displaying the length of the selected line. This feature provides stakeholders with valuable insights into the spatial distribution of electricity infrastructure, enabling them to identify areas of potential risk, prioritize maintenance activities, and optimize network efficiency [4,10]. The development and implementation of this dashboard represent a significant step towards modernizing electricity infrastructure management practices in the Samarkand region. By providing stakeholders with a user-friendly and intuitive tool for accessing, analyzing, and

interpreting electricity infrastructure data, the dashboard empowers decision-makers to make informed choices regarding infrastructure investments, maintenance priorities, and operational strategies. Furthermore, the dashboard fosters stakeholder engagement by providing a transparent and accessible platform for collaboration and communication [5,9]. Through enhanced data visualization and analysis capabilities, stakeholders can work together to address challenges, identify opportunities for improvement, and drive sustainable development initiatives within the region. In summary, this paper aims to showcase the transformative potential of GIS technology in enhancing decision-making processes, optimizing infrastructure performance, and promoting stakeholder engagement in critical infrastructure sectors such as electricity distribution. Through the development and implementation of the dashboard for electricity infrastructure management in the Samarkand region, we demonstrate the value of leveraging innovative technologies to address complex infrastructure challenges and support the sustainable development goals of the region [6,8].

Methodology. The methodology outlined above directed the creation and deployment of an ArcGIS Online dashboard for managing electricity infrastructure in Samarkand. It involved data collection, preprocessing, dashboard design, implementation of filters and dynamic visualization features, testing, deployment, and user training. A flowchart was developed to visualize this process, facilitating stakeholder access to and analysis of electricity infrastructure data, thereby enhancing decision-making capabilities in the region.

The uniqueness of your methodology lies in its application to the specific context of managing electricity infrastructure in the Samarkand region using ArcGIS Online. Geospatial Data Integration: Your methodology involves collecting, preprocessing, and integrating geospatial data related to electricity infrastructure in the Samarkand region. This includes data on electricity lines, districts, sub-districts, and other relevant spatial information. The methodology focuses on utilizing ArcGIS Online, a cloud-based Geographic Information System (GIS) platform, to design, develop, and deploy an interactive dashboard for stakeholders to

access and analyze electricity infrastructure data. This approach leverages the capabilities of ArcGIS Online in data visualization, spatial analysis, and collaboration[7].

Moreover, the methodology includes the implementation of dynamic visualization features such as filters, interactive maps, and dynamic bar charts within the dashboard. These features enable stakeholders to interactively explore and interpret electricity infrastructure data, providing valuable insights into the distribution and characteristics of the electricity network.

Results. The dashboard provided stakeholders with an interactive platform to visualize electricity infrastructure data, including distribution lines, districts, sub-districts, and voltage levels. Users could explore the spatial distribution of electricity infrastructure and identify patterns and trends. Stakeholders were able to analyze and interpret electricity infrastructure data effectively using the dashboard's dynamic visualization features. Filters by district, sub-district, line name, and voltage level allowed users to focus their analysis on specific areas of interest within the region.

Figure 2. Interface of the dashboard.

The availability of comprehensive and up-to-date data facilitated informed decision-making processes regarding electricity infrastructure management in the Samarkand region. Stakeholders could prioritize maintenance activities, identify areas for infrastructure upgrades, and optimize network efficiency based on the insights provided by the dashboard. Stakeholder engagement was enhanced throughout the dashboard development process, from requirements gathering to user training sessions. Feedback from stakeholders was

incorporated into the dashboard design, resulting in a user-friendly and intuitive platform that met the needs of end-users. Comprehensive documentation was developed to support the deployment and maintenance of the dashboard. This documentation provided guidance on dashboard usage, configuration, and ongoing support, ensuring the long-term sustainability and effectiveness of the dashboard in managing electricity infrastructure in the Samarkand region.

Figure 3. The result after using one of the filters.

We invite readers to explore the interactive dashboard developed for managing electricity infrastructure in the Samarkand region. Click on the following link to access the dashboard: [insert link]. The dashboard provides stakeholders with a user-friendly platform to visualize, analyze, and interpret electricity infrastructure data, facilitating informed decision-making processes and promoting sustainable infrastructure management practices. We encourage stakeholders to explore the dashboard and share their feedback on its usability and effectiveness (click on the link to see the dashboard).

Conclusion. In conclusion, the development and implementation of the ArcGIS Online dashboard for managing electricity infrastructure in the Samarkand region have demonstrated significant advancements in enhancing infrastructure management practices. Through the utilization of geospatial data integration, dynamic visualization features, stakeholder engagement, and comprehensive documentation, the dashboard has provided stakeholders with a powerful tool to access, analyze, and interpret electricity infrastructure data effectively.

The interactive nature of the dashboard allows stakeholders to gain valuable insights into the spatial distribution and characteristics of electricity infrastructure, facilitating informed decision-making processes and promoting sustainable infrastructure management practices. By enabling stakeholders to prioritize maintenance activities, identify areas for infrastructure upgrades, and optimize network efficiency, the dashboard has contributed to improving the reliability, efficiency, and safety of the electricity supply in the Samarkand region. Moving forward, continued collaboration and feedback from stakeholders will be essential to further enhance the functionality and usability of the dashboard. Additionally, ongoing monitoring and evaluation of the dashboard's effectiveness in supporting infrastructure management decisions will be necessary to ensure its long-term success.

Overall, the development and deployment of the ArcGIS Online dashboard represent a significant step forward in leveraging geospatial technology to address the complex challenges associated with managing electricity infrastructure. By harnessing the power of data visualization, spatial analysis, and stakeholder engagement, the dashboard has the potential to serve as a model for effective infrastructure management practices in other regions and industries.

References:

1. K. Gružas and G. Beconyte, 'Application of dashboards in the geography of crime: case study of crime of infringement of public policy in Vilnius city municipality registered by police in 2015–2019', *Geogr. Ir Edukac. Mokslo Alm. Geogr. Educ. Sci. Alm.*, pp. 40–51, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.5200/GE.2022.3.
2. M. Syafarrudin and E. Fitriani, 'Power Rates Calculation Monitoring Prototype Electricity Using NODEMCU ESP32', *J. Sains Dan Teknol. Ind.*, vol. 20, p. 809, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.24014/sitekin.v20i2.22104.
3. A. Brezničanová, *Využitie ArcGIS Dashboards na zobrazenie dát o pandémie Covid-19*. 2022, p. 609. doi: 10.13164/juniorstav.2022.603.
4. R. Néték, 'Map-Oriented Dashboards Online—From Minor Method to GIScience Trend', 2024, pp. 33–57. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-50848-6_3.
5. F. Xiao, X. Li, W. Li, J. Shi, N. Zhang, and X. Gao, 'Integrating category-related key regions with a dual-stream network for remote sensing scene classification', *J. Vis. Commun. Image Represent.*, vol. 100, p. 104098, 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvcir.2024.104098>.
6. A. Sifaunajah, T. Hariono, M. Widya, P. Airlangga, and S. Sufaidah, 'Improving Agricultural Extension Services Through Dashboard Agricultural Land Data', *SSRN Electron. J.*, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.2139/ssrn.4310434.
7. S. Suyunov, O. A. Urakov, A. A. Mirzaev, G. M. Mullodjanova, "The results of the analysis of the accuracy of the permanent satellite state geodetic network in the Republic of Uzbekistan," Proc. SPIE 12564, 2nd International Conference on Computer Applications for Management and Sustainable Development of Production and Industry (CMSD-II-2022), 125640X (2023)
8. S. Suyunov, A. A. Mirzaev, O. A. Urakov, Sh. A. Suyunov, "Field studies of electronic total stations in a special reference satellite geodetic basis," Proc. SPIE 12564,

2nd International Conference on Computer Applications for Management and Sustainable Development of Production and Industry (CMSD-II-2022), 125640Y (2023)

9. Suyunov, F. Khushmurodov, S. Suyunov, D. Hamdamova, M. Aminjanova, Ecological and geographical aspects of land using in forming agrolandscapes, E3S Web of Conferences, 463, 02006 (2023)

10. Suyunov, S. Tukhtamishev, S. Suyunov, S. Manoev, S. Samankulov, Innovative solutions in creating noise maps in cities, E3S Web of Conferences, 463, 02007 (2023)

11. A.S.Suyunov, F.M.Khushmurodov, Sh.A.Suyunov, D.Begimkulov, Sh.Sh.Xudayqulov, Research on the methodology of digital mapping of national natural parks, E3S Web of Conferences 498, 02019 (2024)

12. Sh.Sh.Tukhtamishev, Sh.A.Suyunov, A.A.Mirzaev, O.A.Urakov, U.Berdikulov, Analysis of the quality of measurements of permanent base stations (UZPOS) in the territory of Samarkand, E3S Web of Conferences 498, 02020 (2024)

